

SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE BEAM STRUCTURAL RESPONSE DUE TO DEFECTS

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SUMMARY: Composite materials contain defects originating from manufacturing processes and/or inservice life. There is a need for an analytically based acceptance and rejection criterion for composite with a defect. Hence, sensitivity analysis of composite structural response due to defects provides a guideline for this criterion. The focus of this paper is to investigate the change in maximum midplane deflection of a composite beam due to ply angle misorientation, fiber waviness and delamination. An cantilever beam made of IM6/3501-b Gr/ep with $[\pm 45/0/90]_{8s}$ was used to illustrate the developed methodology.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials contain defects originating from manufacturing processes and/or inservice life. Defects such as misarranged fiber orientation, fiber waviness, ply cracking, and delamination can significantly affect the structural response of a system. Instead of re-manufacturing or replacing composite structural components because of defects, designers and engineers want to know what is the overall effect of the defect on the particular system. Therefore, the need for an analytically based acceptance and rejection criterion for composite structures with a defect exists.

In order to quantify the effects of certain parameters on a system, the tools of sensitivity analysis are employed. According to Frank [1], sensitivity analysis provides the basic methods to study the sensitivity of a system to parameter variations. Adelman and Haftka [2] surveyed sensitivity analysis methods applicable to the calculation of structural sensitivity derivatives for structures. Recently, sensitivity analysis has been employed to study the behavior of composite materials. King and Chan[3] studied the effects of taper angle and ply angle orientation on tension and bending loads, Chan and Chou [4] investigated the effects of delamination and fiber waviness on effective axial and bending stiffnesses. Chan and Wang [5] predicted structural properties of laminated composites with fiber waviness.

The focus of this paper is to investigate the change in structural response of a composite beam due to defects. In particular, the effects of ply angle orientation, fiber waviness, and delamination on the maximum midplane deflection of a cantilever composite beam are studied. The maximum midplane deflection equation is derived.

STRUCTURAL RESPONSE OF A CANTILEVER COMPOSITE BEAM

Composite Beam Description

A cantilever composite beam made of IM6/3501-6 graphite epoxy with the lay-up [45/-45/0/90]_{8s} is used. The uniaxial lamina material properties of IM6/3501-6 graphite epoxy are

$$E_1 = 24.8 \times 10^6 \text{ Psi}, E_2 = 1.41 \times 10^6 \text{ Psi}, G_{12} = 0.9 \times 10^6 \text{ Psi}$$

$$\nu_{12} = 0.329, t_{\text{ply}} = 0.0052 \text{ in}, \rho = 0.05 \text{ lbm / in}^3$$

The cantilever composite beam shown in Fig. 1 is loaded laterally with a uniform pressure.

Beam Deflection

The equilibrium equation for the bending of a symmetric laminate under lateral load and with no hygrothermal effects is

$$\frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial x^2} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial y^2} + \frac{q_0}{b} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where q_0 is the uniform load. For a beam subjected to M_x only, the above equation becomes

$$\frac{\partial^4 w_0}{\partial x^4} = \frac{d_{11} q_0}{b} \quad (2)$$

where w_0 is the midplane deflection of the beam and d_{11} is the flexibility of the laminate.

It should be noted that because of anisotropy characteristics, a composite beam will not deflect uniformly across its width. In other words, w_0 is not independent of y . Previous work on the beam deflection, the width effect of the beam is neglected [6,7].

By integrating the above differential equation with the following boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} w_0(0, y) = 0, \quad \frac{\partial w_0(0, y)}{\partial x} = 0 \\ M_x(L, 0) = 0, \quad V_x(L, 0) = 0 \\ \int_{-b/2}^{b/2} \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x \partial y} dy \Big|_{x=L} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

the midplane deflection of a cantilever composite beam as function of x and y can be obtained as

$$w_0(x, y) = \frac{d_{11} q_0 x^4}{24b} + \frac{q_0 x^3}{12b} (d_{16} y - 2d_{11} L) + \frac{q_0 x^2}{8b} (2d_{12} y^2 - d_{16} L y + 2d_{11} L^2) \quad (4)$$

It should be mentioned that the last boundary condition in Equation (3) states that the twisting moment is zero at $x=L$.

The anisotropic coupling terms, d_{12} and d_{16} are generally neglected for orthotropic analysis; however, for beams that are thin and not antisymmetric, neglecting d_{12} and d_{16} can

render non-conservative results [8]. The d_{12} term contributes deflection effects due to Poisson's ratio, and the d_{16} term induces twisting curvature. Note, for beams with a high length to width ratio, the effect of d_{12} is negligible.

By letting $x=L$, the maximum midplane deflection for a cantilever composite beam as a function of y results:

$$w_{max} = \frac{q_0 L^2}{24b} (6d_{12}y^2 - d_{16}Ly + 3d_{11}L^2) \quad (5)$$

SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

Ply Angle Orientation

Effects on Maximum Midplane Deflection

The change in w_{max} due to θ can be obtained by differentiating w_{max} in Eqn. (5) with respect to θ .

$$\frac{\partial w_{max}}{\partial \theta} = \frac{\partial w_{max}}{\partial d_{11}} \cdot \frac{\partial d_{11}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial w_{max}}{\partial d_{12}} \cdot \frac{\partial d_{12}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial w_{max}}{\partial d_{16}} \cdot \frac{\partial d_{16}}{\partial \theta} \quad (6)$$

The derivatives $\partial w_{max}/\partial d_{11}$, $\partial w_{max}/\partial d_{12}$, and $\partial w_{max}/\partial d_{16}$ can be easily obtained and $\partial d_{11}/\partial \theta$, $\partial d_{12}/\partial \theta$ and $\partial d_{16}/\partial \theta$ are given in Reference [3].

Figure 2 depicts normalized w_{max} (@ $y=0$) versus θ for five 0° ply locations. The results indicated that, a maximum w_{max} is found at $\theta = 60.5^\circ$ and w_{max} increases as the location of the 0° ply moves farther away from the laminate midplane. Figure 3 indicates that w_{max} sensitivity to θ increases as the location of the 0° ply moves farther away from the laminate midplane. Figure 4 show normalized w_{max} versus width for a thick laminate $[45, -45, 0, 90]_{8s}$ and a thin laminate $[45, -45, 0, 90]_{2s}$. As expected, maximum w_{max} does not occur at $y = 0$ due to beam twist (i.e. the d_{16} term). As the beam becomes thinner, the twist becomes more unsymmetrical and the maximum w_{max} shifts farther from the center of the beam.

Fiber Waviness

The geometry of fiber waviness shown in Figure 5 is defined by a sinusoidal wave function in the principal material axis. The fiber orientation ϕ at any given position is defined in Ref. [5] as

$$\phi = \tan^{-1} \left[\pi R \cos \left(\frac{\pi x}{L} \right) \right], \quad R = A/L \quad (7)$$

where R is the fiber waviness factor. It is assumed that all fibers in a given lamina have the same wave function, and the wave functions are parallel throughout the lamina.

Effects on Maximum Midplane Deflection

The change in w_{max} due to R is defined by

$$\frac{\partial w_{max}}{\partial R} = \frac{\partial w_{max}}{\partial d_{11}} \cdot \frac{\partial d_{11}}{\partial R} \quad (8)$$

The terms $\partial d_{11}/\partial R$ and $\partial w_{max}/\partial d_{11}$ were explicitly obtained and given in Ref. [9].

The result shown in Fig. 6 indicates that w_{max} sensitivity to R increases as the ply containing the fiber waviness is placed further away from the laminate midplane.

Delamination

All analysis in this section is based on the assumption that delaminations exist symmetrically in the beam cross section as shown in Fig. 7. This assumption prevents coupling and subsequent introduction of a global [B] matrix.

Structural Response Sensitivity to Delamination Length

Utilizing the following continuity conditions at $x = c$

$$w_0^I = w_0^{II} \quad , \quad \frac{\partial w_0^I}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial w_0^{II}}{\partial x} \quad (9)$$

the midplane deflection for the beam shown in Fig. 7 can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} w_0^{II} &= \frac{d_{11}^{II} q_0 x^4}{24b} + \frac{q_0 x}{6b} [c^3 (d_{11}^I - d_{11}^{II}) - d_{11}^I L^3] + \\ &\quad \frac{q_0}{8b} [c^4 (d_{11}^{II} - d_{11}^I) - d_{11}^I L^4] \quad \text{for} \quad 0 \leq x \leq c \\ w_0^I &= \frac{d_{11}^I q_0}{24b} (x^4 - 4L^3 x + 3L^4) \quad \text{for} \quad c \leq x \leq L \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The maximum midplane deflection (w_{max}) occurs at $x=0$ is

$$w_{max} = \frac{q_0}{8b} [(d_{11}^{II} - d_{11}^I) c^4 + d_{11}^I L^4] \quad (11)$$

It should be noted that all the d_{11} 's are function of delamination width, a . The sensitivity of the maximum midplane deflection (w_{max}) to delamination length is defined by

$$\frac{\partial w_{max}}{\partial c} = \frac{q_0 c^3}{2b} (d_{11}^{II} - d_{11}^I) \quad (12)$$

Figure 8 depicts normalized w_{max} versus normalized delamination length (c/L) at the following four ply interfaces:

- 1) 90/45 Interface between plies 28 & 29
- 2) 45/-45 Interface between plies 29 & 30

- 3) -45/0 Interface between plies 30 & 31
- 4) 0/90 Interface between plies 31 & 32

The delamination width a remains constant @ $a = 0.2$ in. An interesting observation is made from Figure 8. For delamination occurring at the 0/90 and 90/45 ply interfaces, w_{max} decreases as the delamination length is increased. This observation implies that the beam actually becomes stiffer as the delamination length is increased for delamination at the 0/90 and 90/45 ply interfaces. The 0/90 ply interface is the most sensitive to delamination length, and the 45/-45 ply interface is the least sensitive to delamination length. For the other two ply interfaces, -45/0 and +45/-45, w_{max} increases as the delamination length increases. Figure 9 exhibits w_{max} sensitivity to delamination length vs. normalized delamination length (c/L). At all interfaces, sensitivity to delamination length is not significant until $c/L=0.3$. Similar results to Figure 10 are obtained.

CONCLUSIONS

Closed-form solutions for sensitivity analysis were developed to quantify the effects of defects on the structural response of composite beams. An expression of a cantilevered composite beam deflection accounting for the width effect was also developed. The following conclusions were deduced for a rectangular cantilever composite beam made of IM6/3501-6 graphite epoxy with the lay-up $[45/-45/0/90]_8s$

- 1) The location of the maximum midplane deflection shifts away from the center of the beam width when the laminate with the same layup becomes thinner.
- 2) The maximum midplane deflection sensitivity to ply angle orientation and fiber waviness increases as the ply containing the ply angle orientation or fiber waviness is located farther away from the laminate midplane.
- 3) For delamination occurring at 0/90 and 90/45 ply interfaces, maximum midplane deflection decreases as the delamination length increases, implying that the beam actually becomes stiffer.
- 4) For delamination occurring at -45/0 and 45/-45 ply interfaces, maximum midplane deflection increases as the delamination length.

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Figure 1. Schematic of Cantilever Composite Beam

Figure 2. Normalized Maximum Midplane Deflection vs. Ply Angle Orientation (0-90 Degrees)

Figure 3. Maximum Midplane Deflection Sensitivity to Ply Angle Orientation (0-5 Degrees)

Figure 4. Normalized Maximum Midplane Deflection vs. Width

Figure 5. Geometry of Fiber Waviness

Figure 6. Maximum Midplane Deflection Sensitivity to Fiber Waviness Factor

Figure 7. Cantilever Beam With Delaminations

Figure 8. Normalized Maximum Midplane Deflection vs. Delamination Length

Figure 9. Maximum Midplane Deflection Sensitivity to Delamination Length